

Mendeley

Management Reference Mendeley dan Zotero

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Universitas Lambung Mangkurat Banjarmasin

MENDELEY
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Mengapa menggunakan tools “Mendeley” dan “Zotero”

1. Format “Mazab” Primer dan Mutakhir
2. Konsisten
3. Menghindari referensi “tidak dikutip”
4. Data rujukan tersimpan dalam library online

Posisi Tools Mendeley/ Zotero dalam karya ilmiah

1. Title
 - a. Abstrak
 - b. Kata Kunci
 2. Introduction
 3. Method
 4. Result and Discussion
 5. Bibliografi
 - a. Citation
 - b. Bibliografi
-] → Mendeley/ Zotero

Mendeley

1. Mendeley menggunakan dua cara yaitu mendeley desktop dan fitur terbaru yaitu Mendeley Reference Manager
2. Mendeley desktop sampai saat ini masih bisa digunakan
3. Mendeley Reference Manager yang dirilis tahun 2019 menggunakan aplikasi add on pada ms word
4. Mendeley tidak lagi ada profil tetapi langsung masuk di mendeley library

Mendeley

The screenshot shows the Mendeley website's download page for Windows. The browser address bar displays "mendeley.com/download-desktop-new/". The page header includes the Mendeley logo, navigation links for "Solutions", "Support", "Sign In", and "Create account", and a "Download" button. The main heading is "Download Mendeley Desktop for Windows". Below this is an illustration of a laptop with a Windows logo on the screen and a Mendeley icon in a dashed circle. A red button labeled "Download Mendeley Desktop for Windows" is positioned below the illustration. Underneath the button, the text reads "Windows 7, 8.1 and 10 (Version 1803) [See release notes.](#)". Further down, it lists "Other systems:" with links for "Mendeley Desktop for macOS" (with an Apple logo) and "Mendeley Desktop for Linux" (with a Linux logo). At the bottom, a blue banner contains the text "New Mendeley Reference Manager is now available" and a "Get started" button.

Mendeley

The screenshot shows the Mendeley website's download page for the Reference Manager. The browser address bar displays "mendeley.com/download-reference-manager". The page features the Mendeley logo and navigation links for Solutions, Support, Sign In, Create account, and a Download button. The main heading is "Mendeley Reference Manager", followed by a prominent "Download now for Windows" button. Below this, it specifies "Windows 7 and above" and provides a link to "See release notes". An illustration of a laptop with the Mendeley logo on the screen and a document is shown to the right. A section for "Other Systems" includes links for "Mendeley Reference Manager for macOS" (with an Apple logo) and "Mendeley Reference Manager for Linux" (with a penguin logo). A note states "Mendeley Desktop is still available" with a "Learn more" link. The bottom section is titled "Your new Mendeley Reference Manager" and features icons representing document management and synchronization. On the right side of this section, there is a partially visible link that says "Activate Go to Setti".

Mendeley

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